

THE ROLE OF EDUCATORS OF THE PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATION IN SOCIAL ACTIVITIES WITH CHILDREN

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Annotation: this article we can learn about what future educators need to pay attention to when educating a harmonious generation, and what a future educator-pedagogue should be like.

Keywords: educator, educator, preschool educational organizations, ethics, physical development, pedagogical science.

Аннотация: В этой статье мы можем узнать, на что следует обращать внимание будущим педагогам при воспитании гармоничного поколения и каким должен быть будущий педагог-педагог.

Ключевые слова: воспитатель, педагог, дошкольные образовательные организации, нравственность, физическое развитие, педагогическая наука.

The upbringing of a perfect person is a long-standing dream of our ancestors, and from the moment the child comes to the universe, he was taught the laws of good manners, physical and spiritual development fanatically. In the structure of pedagogical science, the pre-school pedagogical Fen was created, which deals with the problems of upbringing preschool children. The science of preschool pedagogy is an inherited wealth for the future, for the future. The value of this wealth is so great that it makes a person spiritually rich, filling his heart with happiness, divine light. There is no one in the world who does not have a mentor. Whether he is the leader of the government, the great allomami, the doctor, the writer who won the people's race, or the poor hand of flowers, let him be the mentor of all and all, and the guide who lives his life path. The greatest duty of the master is to prepare intelligent, capable and authentic disciples who will touch the people. The educator performs the same important and honorable task as raising the younger generation as worthy children of our people. The political maturity of the educator contributes to the realization of his responsibility to the people and society for the quality of raising children, constantly activating his skills in a creative approach to solving educational work and promoting the growth of colleagues at work. The educator must be socially active to understand the factors of nature and society, knowing the life of the land in which he lives.[1]

For their achievements in the upbringing of the younger generation in a harmonious way, for their creative work in the work of a pedagogue, for their achievements in the generalization of advanced experience, teachers are awarded such honorable titles as 'Methodist teacher', 'senior teacher', 'Methodist - educator', etc. President Of The Republic Of Uzbekistan Sh .M. With the initiatives of Mirziyoyev, the monthly salaries of pedagogical workers in our republic are increased from year to year and the living conditions are improved. Scientific and methodological Centers for professional development of pedagogical workers are being expanded, the demand for their political training is increasing, conditions are being created

for them to undergo retraining every 4-5 years. The qualitative changes and efficiency in the education and education of preschool children are higher by harmonizing more with the roots of our national pedagogical history and achievements in the field of modern education. The theoretical foundations of preschool pedagogy are aimed at exalting the mental maturation of a person. The national foundations of preschool pedagogy are based on folk heritage and universal values.[2]

Today, simultaneously with the experience of developed foreign countries in improving and stabilizing the activities of the new education system and ensuring the rights of citizens to receive knowledge, it is necessary to use the invaluable heritage of our thinker ancestors in the East. As our president rightly noted in his works 'High spirituality is the power that cannot be overcome', 'if the greatest among the world leaders is the school, the most important among the professions is teaching and coaching, I think we will tell the same truth'

In chindan, a nation that is not neutral to its tomorrow's future, a nation that sees its bright and prosperous days in the perspective of its owners, the younger generation, pays special attention to education and upbringing.

The educator performs a responsible task along with an important, proud work, preparing our younger generation as worthy children of our people. The political maturity of the educator contributes to the awareness of his responsibility to the people and society for the quality of raising children, a creative approach to educational tasks, constant improvement of his skills and the growth of his comrades at work. So, the educator must first of all be educated, know the enormous life in which he lives, understand the laws of nature and society, be socially active, master the pedagogy of general and preschool education, the psyche and physiology of children, and know the age characteristics of children.[3] Also, the approach of the pedagogical educator to the analysis of phenomena from a scientific point of view makes it possible to realize the success of the comprehensive development of the child. The issue of the pedagogical skills of a preschooler in the process of continuing education is one of the widely studied areas and is characterized by the development of a specific pedagogical system.

K.Hashimov, R.M. Qadirava, F.R. Qadirava, N.SH. Nurmukhammedova, M.Ochilov, S.Temirova, O.Mosurmanova, S.Nishanova, U.Inkamav, M.Inamava, M.Goranov, S.Ochilov, N.Artiqav, Q.Gurbanbaev, J.Tashmatova, Sh.Scientists such as Olimov did the work. A well-known pedagogue, a methodologist who developed methods and methodologies for teaching children to the mother tongue, a famous specialist in preschool education, professor Y.I.Tikheyeva, giving a high assessment of the educator's speech, said: a model that children involuntarily imitate in kindergarten is the language of the educator (gardener), the educator's language should be one that combines in itself everything that has an incredibly effective and incredibly strong effect on the language of children. The language of the gardener should be fluffy, free from any defects of literary pronunciation. The educator is the main person in the organization of preschool education. The quality of the entire ideological and educational work, and, moreover, the level of upbringing and knowledge of the future generation, depends on the ideological and political and scientific preparedness of the Educator, his sense of responsibility, pedagogical skills and creative attitude to work. The child's attitude to educational activities is more determined by his attitude to the person of the educator.

A distinctive feature of the educator is his high professional skills. The most important thing is to know the psyche of the child, age and specific psychophysiological characteristics. With the

kindergarten program being formed taking into account the age, physical and mental characteristics of children, one cannot foresee at what time and how a separate mental trait is manifested in each child, this work is entrusted to a well-prepared educator in the program. The educator creates good conditions for the good development of each child in his group from the physical side, good functioning of his higher nervous activity, as well as normal upbringing from the mental, moral, labor, aesthetic side. Children of each age group interact with their caregivers in household-economic, labor, game activities. The educator organizes a children's game, reads or tells works of art. In this process, both the good and the defects of the educator's speech are clearly manifested, and these features are reflected in the speech of the educators. Hence, the speech characteristics of kindergarten teachers depend on the speech of the educator in full. The educator's speech, which is always the focus of children's attention, is an example of cultural speech for children. The educator should always look at his speech from a critical point of view, and if he notices a deficiency in his speech, try to eliminate it immediately.

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